

Abbas Nazarian Madavani, **Maryam Mokhtari Dinani**, (2014). [Preferences Coaching Behaviors Iranian Volleyball Players](#), [Sport Management studies](#), 6 (25): 39-52.

Preferences Coaching Behaviors Iranian Volleyball Players

Abbas Nazarian Madavani¹ - Maryam Mokhtari Dinani²

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study was studying of preferences Coaching Behaviors Iranian Volleyball Players. Research method was descriptive-Correlation method. According to Iranian federation volleyball, statistical population was 1200 peoples of volleyball players of serious grads teams. 320 athletes (160 men and 160 women) from 26 team participated as statistical sample in this study according to Krejcie and Morgan's table. Data collecting instrument was Coaching Behavior questionnaire built by Martin, S.B., & Barnes, K. (1999) and researcher-built demographic questionnaire.

The results indicated that players preferred to observed higher frequency of Reinforcement, Mistake–Contingent technical instruction, General technical instruction, keeping control, behaviors styles. On the other hand, they don't like Punishment and Punitive technical instruction, ignoring mistakes, Non – Reinforcement behaviors style. The results show, also, Women players was different with men players in some of subscales coaching behaviors. Women players preferred to observed higher frequency of Reinforcement, Mistake–Contingent technical instruction, keeping control, behaviors styles more than men players. On the other hand, the men players preferred to observed higher frequency of Non – Reinforcement behaviors and punitive technical instruction style.

It seems that successful in professional sports levels will happen with adapting coach behaviors patterns with athlete's expectations and focus on Reinforcement and instruction approach.

Keywords: Coaching Behaviors, Volleyball, Primary League

¹ . Assistant Professor of Shahid Rajaei University, Email: Abbasnazarian@Sru.ac.ir

² . Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@alzahra.ac.ir